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Microstructural Evolutions of Weld Metal in SAE1080 Steel

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Abstract

A permanent connection like a welding joint is very important in various industries. The metallurgical microstructure is one of the important characteristics of weld metal. Due to the strong influence of microstructure on the development of mechanical properties, microstructural evolutions of weld metal have always been of interest to researchers. The CO₂ arc welding process has many applications in various industries. The effect of welding parameters, including arc voltage (V) (23, 25, and 27 V), welding current (I) (100, 110, and 120 A), and welding speed (S) (42, 62, and 82 cm/min) on microstructural evolutions of the weld metal in SAE1080 steel was evaluated in this paper. The results clearly showed that the microstructure of the weld metal in all tests was mainly composed of retained austenite (RA), martensite (M), and tempered martensite (TM) phases, and changing each of the welding parameters had a significant effect on the volume fraction and morphology of phases.

Keywords: CO₂ arc welding process, welding parameters, weld metal, microstructure, SAE1080 steel.

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Introduction

Among the joining processes, welding is very important because of its high joint efficiency, simple set up, flexibility, and low fabrication cost [1]. A lot of materials can be joined using various welding processes, including friction stir welding (FSW), friction stir spot welding (FSSW), ultrasonic welding (USW), tungsten inert gas (TIG), laser beam welding (LBW), metal inert gas (MIG), metal active gas (MAG), and arc stud welding (ASW) which all of the processes have different advantages and disadvantages in terms of cost, appropriateness, labor, training, efficiency, time, temperature, and simplicity [2–7]. Among the welding processes, gas-metal arc welding (GMAW) is the preferred process for a wide range of ferrous and non-ferrous metal products [8,9] due to its high deposition efficiency, better welding quality [10,11], low cost, high efficiency of the joining process [12], high speed [13], and high productivity rate [14]. In this process, a continuous welding wire with a diameter between 0.8 and 1.6 mm is used as filler metal. The heat of an electric arc is used to melt the tip of the filler metal and the surface of the base materials to form weld metal that is protected by a shielding gas. Due to the strong influence of microstructure on the development of mechanical properties, microstructural evolutions of weld metal have always been of interest to researchers. To the best of our knowledge, relatively little information is available on the microstructure of the weld metal in high-carbon steels. In this paper, an attempt has been made to study the effect of CO₂ arc welding process parameters on the microstructure of the weld metal in SAE1080 steel.

Materials and methods

In this study, SAE1080 steel plates with a thickness of 4 mm and chemical composition of 0.81C-0.22Si-0.65Mn-0.01P-0.01S (%wt.) were used as the base material, and ER70S-6 (AWS A5.18 standard) with a diameter of 1.2 mm and a chemical composition of 0.11C-1.63Mn-0.95Si-0.5Cu-0.035P-0.025S (%wt.) was used as filler metal. A robotic CO₂ arc welding process was used to join the base materials as multi-pass butt joints in the flat position. As in our previous studies (see [15–18]), the welding operation in this study was performed by means of a SOS Model DR Series ARK ROBO-1500 welding robot with a capacity of 0–600 A and 0–50 V ranges. To avoid welding distortion, the test plates were fixed in the fixture jig before the welding process. Welding samples were produced in different combinations of V (23, 25, and 27 V), I (100, 110, and 120 A), and S (42, 62, and 82 cm/min). To evaluate the microstructure of the weld metal, the cross-section of the welding joints was first cleaned, grounded through 200–1000 mesh using grinding papers, polished through 1 μm diamond paste, etched with 2 % Nital for 6 s, and investigated by optical microscope observations using OPT microscope.

Results and discussion

The results of this paper are shown in Fig. 1. As shown, the microstructure of the weld metal in all conditions was mainly composed of the M, RA, and TM phases. Increasing the V and/or I and decreasing the S increased the volume fraction of the RA and TM phases, and slightly coarsened the microstructure of the weld metal. This evolution can be related to the influence of the welding parameters on the welding heat input (H) and the cooling rate (CR) of the weld metal. H increases with increasing V and/or I and decreasing S. The most important feature of the H is that it governs the CR of the weld metal [19]. The CR in the fusion welding process is the primary factor that determines the microstructure and mechanical properties of a weld metal [19]. An increase in the H and thus a decrease in the CR of the weld metal promoted the formation of RA and TM phases. Coarsening of the microstructure was also observed with the increase of H.

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Figure (1) Microstructural evolutions of the weld metal in SAE1080 steel (25 V, 62 cm/min, a.100, b.110, and c.120 A) (110 A, 62 cm/min, d.23, e.25, and f.27 V) (25 V, 110 A, g.42, h.62, and i.82 cm/min)

Conclusions

The CO₂ arc welding process has many parameters that can affect the microstructure of the weld metal. In the present study, the effect of V, I, and S on the microstructure of weld metals produced by this process in SAE1080 steel was investigated. The results showed that the microstructure of the weld metal in all conditions mainly consisted of M, TM, and RA phases. Increasing the V and/or I, and decreasing the S increased the volume fraction of RA and TM phases and slightly coarsened the microstructure of the weld metals.

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